

Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

Data and digitalisation provide an important opportunity for animal disease prevention and control, through data-driven decision making. Within the research project "DigiVet", workshops were held with various stakeholders in the UK, Sweden and Denmark to identify challenges and opportunities along the data lifecycle (from acquisition to maintenance, analysis and return value). This policy brief provides key messages to inform policy makers of our findings.

MAJOR FINDINGS

Different data sources are of relevance for animal disease prevention, depending on the disease in question. Examples include livestock movement data, animal disease surveillance data, meat inspection data, data on wildlife, and geographical data. There are different challenges in the digitalisation processes for each of these, which are important to overcome to make data and results from data analysis accessible to the right stakeholders and decision makers. During stakeholder workshops, the most common challenges that were raised were legal and technical barriers in data sharing between authorities (and private organisations), as well as deficient data quality. Modification of policies and legislation to streamline data sharing may provide an opportunity to overcome legal barriers, but interpretation of legal frameworks is a further challenge. Technical solutions may enhance data sharing while providing a mechanism for compliance with relevant policies. Clarity is needed regarding what public (not necessarily open) data is available and who is the owner, as well as who has the responsibility to build technical solutions to manage or analyse the data. Good data quality relies on controls in every step of the data lifecycle, from the early acquisition phase all the way through to management of archived data. This can partially be achieved by legislation mandating certain levels of quality control, but will likely also require also incentivisation (including via return value) directly to those providing data.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Digitalisation processes are likely to change current practices of data usage and decision making. They are a continuously ongoing process that should be continuously re-evaluated and improved as necessary. The results also indicate that in some cases it is important to modify legislation to enable data sharing to essential stakeholders.

IMPORTANT ASSUMPTIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Stakeholders in the workshops were mainly from governmental organisations and organisations representing animal owners or veterinarians, including farming organisations and academic groups. The research project DigiVet is continuing until the end of 2023 and further results are expected in conjunction with further workshops.

KEY MESSAGES

- **Digitalisation of data and workflows provide opportunities** to improve data quality, reduce the requirement for manual intervention, and to share data in a more secure and streamlined way. High-quality data that is accessible for the right stakeholders and decision makers is important to ensure animal and human health, economic security and food safety.
- **Enhanced data sharing** between relevant stakeholders and decision makers is important, but both legal and technical challenges exist. Technical solutions and changes in legislation both provide opportunities to improve data sharing.
- **Data quality can be improved** through improved incentivisation and return value to those providing the data, as well as legislation to ensure data control. It is essential to maintain high quality throughout the entire data lifecycle.

OBJECTIVES

The research project DigiVet aims to improve global health and food safety outcomes by developing future-proof data infrastructure and analytics within the veterinary public sector. The objectives of the workshops summarised in this policy brief were to explore challenges in data digitalisation and to identify key opportunities for developing technical solutions within and beyond the project.

LINKS TO EXISTING REPORTS

Mapping data ecosystems and associated regulatory frameworks: <https://zenodo.org/record/7462364>

Stakeholder workshop reports:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/digivet>

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